

The Effect of Talent Management and Knowledge Management on Employee Performance with Employee Engagement as Mediation Variable in BPJS Yogyakarta Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of talent management and knowledge management mediated by employee engagement on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta. This study used a descriptive quantitative approach, the population in this study were BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta employees, totaling 42 permanent employees. Researchers determine the number of research samples using non-probability sampling technique. The non-probability sampling technique that the researchers used in this study was saturated or census sampling. The sample used was all employees of the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS, namely 42 employees. The data used are primary data obtained through questionnaires and interviews. The analytical method used in this study is the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with Partial Least Square (PLS) 4.0. The results of this study indicate that talent management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, talent management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with employee engagement as the mediating variable, knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with employee engagement as a mediating variable.

KEYWORDS: Employee engagement, Employee performance, Knowledge management, Talent management.

INTRODUCTION

Every agency or company is always effective in implementing programs that are managed to achieve company goals. One way is to increase employee performance. Employee performance reflects the ability of employees to complete all tasks that are their responsibility. In companies, when employee performance is optimal and increases, the company's organizational performance also increases. Every organizational activity is always influenced by various changes in the internal and external environment. Every company must pay attention to employee performance because it can determine the success of the company's organization in order to reach the highest level in accordance with the goals that have been set optimally (Ribka Laura, 2021).

The Employment Social Security Administration Agency (BPJS) is a public legal entity that operates in the field of administering employment social security. Before becoming a public legal entity, it was originally a PT. Jamsostek (Persero) which was founded in 1947 and then transformed into BPJS Ketenagakerjaan which was formed based on Law No. 24 of 2011. BPJS Ketenagakerjaan has operational regional offices in various regions of Indonesia to serve social security for workers. One of its branch offices is located in the Special Region of Yogyakarta (DIY). As the main branch office in the DY area, it certainly requires employees who are energetic, dedicated, proactive,

The performance of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta has fluctuated in terms of performance achievements in 2019-2022. The occurrence of fluctuations in the results of these performance achievements can be seen as described in Table 1.1 below:

Table 1.1.

No	Performance Target Perspective	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	Customer Perspective	59.10%	48.32%	55.38%	60.02%
2	Internal Process Perspective	13.02%	15.37%	14.45%	12.30%
3	Growth and Learning Perspectives	12.87%	16.30%	14.67%	12.05%
4	Financial Perspective	13.01%	10.27%	12.50%	15.07%
	Total	98.00%	90.26%	97.00%	99.44%

Based on Table 1.1, it shows that seen from the performance achievements of the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS in 2019-2022 as a whole there have been fluctuations in terms of performance achievements, especially the customer perspective. Based on *core* the field undertaken by BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, in addition to carrying out government functions (governing function) also carries out functions in the field of public services (public services), namely the status of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan as a public legal entity that carries out public service functions in the field of administering social security. So, this certainly greatly influences the performance of employees in the service division. When the performance of the service division is good, it will also lead to a good customer perspective, and vice versa when their performance drops, it will make customers give bad perspective feedback. Besides that, the thing that needs to be considered is that the total achievement that is the target has not yet reached 100 percent during the period from 2019 to 2022.

This is reinforced by the situation where employee performance has also fluctuated in the last 4 years. The data is presented in the form of Table 1.2 as follows:

Table 1.2 Employee Achievement Targets of Yogyakarta Employment BPJS

No	Membership Type	YEAR			
		2019	2020	2021	2022
1	Wage Recipient	266,197	281,179	279,936	282,731
2	Not a Wage Recipient	24,080	22,659	23,764	25,890
3	Construction service	62,787	78,873	78,378	80012
Total Active Workforce		353,064	382,711	382,078	388,633
Employee Achievement (%)		31.6%	34.23%	34.17%	36.17%

The Employment BPJS program is aimed at wage-earning workers, non-wage workers and construction service workers. Based on Table 1.2, it can be seen that the achievements of employees at the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS over the last 4 years have been fluctuating or unstable. In 2019 the total registered active workforce was 31.6%, increasing to 34.23% in 2020 but decreased to 34.17% in 2021 and then increased again to 36.17%. Regarding this achievement target, based on interviews with Mr. Afriyandi Setiawan as the General Affairs and Human Resources section on Friday 13 March 2023, for the last 4 years the achievements of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta employees have not reached the specified target figures and are still experiencing fluctuations so that in this case employee performance has not been maximized.

BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta *employee performance* assessed from the aspect of KPI (Key Performance Indicator) and KBI (Key Behavior Indicator) methods that are generally applied by most companies to assess the progress of a company and employee performance in it. (<http://www.bpjsketenagakerjaan.go.id>). The following is the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS Employee Performance data for 2020-2021 as follows:

Table 1.3. Criteria Final Score

Final Performance score
Not Enough (Merit Rating : < 2,5)
Enough (Merit Rating : 2,5 < 3,5)
Good (Merit Rating : 3,5 < 4)
Satisfy (Merit Rating : 4 < 4,5)
Very Satisfactory (Merit Rating : 4 < 4,5)
Excellent (Merit Rating : 4 < 4,5)

Based on the KPI table (*Key Performance Indicators*) above regarding the results of the employee performance assessment for 2020 and 2021, there are several employees' performance, namely as many as 14, which have decreased in terms of their KPI values from 2020 to 2021. Based on interviews conducted with Mr. Afriyandi Setiawan as an employee of the General Affairs and Human Resources BPJS Yogyakarta KACAB Employment on March 15 2023 said that there were several employees who chatted a lot with

colleagues, both in one division and another division during working hours. In addition, there are still obstacles faced by workers such as when someone is transferred, employees meet with superiors who are difficult to work with. Based on information from Mr. Afriyandi,

Based on these problems it can be seen that *employee performance* is one of the benchmarks to determine the value of the success of an organization, in which the organization must be able to create good employee performance in order to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. According to Simanjuntak (2005), there are three factors that can affect employee performance, namely: first, individual factors, second, organizational support, and third, management support. Of the three factors, what caught the attention of researchers was the management support factor. Lewis & Heckman, (2006) argues that management support can start from the recruitment process, employee placement, performance appraisal, training and career development, until employees leave the company.

Such a strategy can be implemented by management through employee talent management (*talent management*). Talent management is identifying, developing, retaining and placing the right people in the right places. Thus talent management is concerned with finding the right people with the right skills for the right positions. The higher the company's attention to talent management, the more highly talented employees can look for from outside as well as from training and regeneration (Busro, 2018).

Table 1.4. The Problems of Knowledge Management BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Yogyakarta

Indicator	Problem
personal knowledge	There are differences in understanding between one employee and another regarding the work to be carried out because the level of personal knowledge of employees is different from one another
Work procedures	Submission of less detail so that it confuses the recipient of the information so that it has an impact on performance in serving
Technology	The use of the internet which is still often misused by employees for purposes other than work.

In addition to implementing the existencetalent managementand knowledge management in maintaining employee performance. Employee performance will also be influenced by the organization's success in creating employee engagement. Employee engagement plays an important role in achieving organizational goals, building effective teams, healthy interpersonal relationships between colleagues and managers and a good work environment within the organization so that it can affect employee performance (Nidan, 2016).

Some literature shows thatemployee performanceinfluenced by talent management, knowledge management and employee engagement. Like the research conducted by Choirun et al., (2016) found that talent management and knowledge management have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Research by Allameh et al. (2014) showed that there was a positive impact on employee engagement on employee performance. Many studies have proven a significant relationship between talent management and knowledge management (Nzewi et al., 2015; Torabi et al., 2016; Ahmad & Anwar, 2018).

But empirical studies involvingemployee engagementin relation to talent management and knowledge management on employee performance simultaneously is still very limited. Research conducted by Sumarto & Rumaningsih, (2021) shows that there is a direct and indirect positive and significant influence between talent management and knowledge management on employee performance through employee engagement as a mediating variable. Whereas research by Khairina & Games, (2022) shows there is a difference, namely talent management has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance through employee engagement as a mediating variable and Abdullahi et al.'s research, (2022) also shows that employee engagement does not mediate some of the relationship between talent management indicator.

This made the researchers want to conduct research whether talent management and knowledge management have an effect on the potential to increase employee performance and whether the existence of employee engagement can directly or indirectly affect employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta, so researchers are interested in conducting research on the

influence Talent Management and Knowledge Management on Employee Performance through Employee Engagement at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Yogyakarta.

HYPHOTESIS FORMULATION

1. The direct influence of Talent Management on Employee Performance

Talent management is an important matter related to the management of human resources as an asset of a company or organization. Improving employee performance cannot be separated from talent management. If talent management can be carried out in an integrated and appropriate manner, it can improve employee performance. Vice versa if talent management is not implemented properly, employee performance will decrease (Harmen, 2018). Research by Mangusho, et.al (2015) found that talent management practices such as job rotation, organizations can increase employee competence which has an impact on achieving high employee performance. The research also shows a positive and significant relationship between talent management and employee performance.

This is also supported by Nzewi, et.al (2015) whose research results show a significant positive relationship between talent management and employee performance at commercial banks in Asaba, Nigeria. In addition, the results of research by (Abdullahi et al., 2022; Khairina & Games, 2022; Hussain Hakro et al., 2022) also show that there is a positive and significant effect between talent management on employee performance.

2. Direct influence of Knowledge Management on Employee Performance

The role of knowledge management is very important in organizational life as a form of strategy in improving employee performance. "Knowledge Management can improve skills and work motivation so as to encourage increased individual and organizational performance. Employee performance will achieve maximum results if it is supported by the knowledge it has, but vice versa if knowledge management is not good, it will have an impact on decreasing performance (Falah, 2017).

This has also been recognized by Ahmad & Anwar, (2018) which shows the results of research that knowledge management practices such as sharing of knowledge and use of technology have a positive and significant impact on employee performance working in the software industry in Pakistan. This proves that knowledge management and employee performance have a direct relationship. Likewise, research conducted by Torabi et al., (2016) which tested the impact of knowledge management on employee performance showed a positive and significant effect. Likewise Sahana S. C & Menon, (2018) found a positive correlation between knowledge management and employee performance.

3. Indirect influence of Talent Management on Employee Performance through Employee Engagement as a mediating variable

Research conducted by Hussain Hakro et al., (2022) The results showed that all relationships between talent management on employee performance and employee engagement as mediating variables tested positive and significant including direct and indirect relationships because the mediation effect of employee engagement proved positive and significant with talent management. The results of Choirun et al.'s research (2016) also show that talent management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

4. Indirect influence of Talent Management on Employee Performance through Employee Engagement as a mediating variable

Sumarto & Rumaningsih, (2021) found that there were direct and indirect impacts on the talent management and knowledge management variables indicating that both paths were effective, so that the talent management and knowledge management variables needed to be maintained. This research also shows that there is a direct and indirect positive and significant influence between talent management and knowledge management on employee performance, so that employee engagement mediation as a mediating variable is a partial mediation. The results of this study are supported by research by Choirun et al., (2016) which shows knowledge management also has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Figure 1. Framework

METHOD

This type of research is quantitative research. The object of research in this study is the influence of Talent Management and Knowledge Management as independent variables, Employee Performance as the dependent variable and Employee Engagement as a mediating variable. This research was conducted at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Yogyakarta. The population in this study are all permanent employees of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Yogyakarta totaling 42 employees. This study took a population sample. In order to produce more effective and efficient research and produce unbiased results, sampling was conducted. This study uses a saturated sampling technique, which means that each population is considered as a sample

Collecting data using a questionnaire consisting of two parts. The first part collects demographic information of the respondents, such as gender, age, last education level, position, years of service in last position. The second part includes research indicators for each of the variables tested. In BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Yogyakarta, researchers directly distributed questionnaires to respondents.

Data analysis used Smart PLS which was tested in three stages. First test the outer model with three methods used to measure the feasibility of the instrument. The criteria used to assess convergent validity with a loading factor ≥ 0.50 , composite reliability with Cronbach Alpha ≥ 0.60 or $\rho_{cc} \geq 0.70$, and discriminant validity with AVE ≥ 0.50 . Second, test the inner model by conducting the R Square, Q Square and Goodness of Fit tests.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Description of Respondents

This research was conducted on 42 employees BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Yogyakarta. Researchers obtained data by distributing questionnaires directly to 42 employees. To find out the characteristics of the respondents, a descriptive statistical test was carried out. This test is done to find out gender, age, last education level, position, years of service in last position. The following are the results of the respondent characteristic test.

The characteristics of employees can be seen from the gender group, most of the Yogyakarta Employment BPJS employees are men with a percentage of 52%, totaling 22 people. When viewed by age group, most of the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS employees are in the age group of 31 to 35 years, with a percentage of 26%, as many as 11 people. Based on the last educational

level group, most of the Yogyakarta Employment BPJS employees have an undergraduate education level with a percentage of 71.43% as many as 30 people. Most of the positions of the Yogyakarta Employment BPJS employees are in the Special Account Representative positions with a percentage of 19% as many as 8 people.

Validity Test

Figure 2. Output outer loading

The results of the instrument test is the convergent validity approach has a loading factor value of > 0.7 for all variable items of talent management, knowledge management, employee engagement, and employee performance, so that the research data meets the convergent validity criteria. Composite reliability test results as a whole have a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60 orpc > 0.70, so the research data meets the composite reliability criteria. Meanwhile, the overall discriminant validity test has an AVE value of > 0.50, so that it fits the discriminant validity criteria. Therefore, the research data has fulfilled the instrument criteria, so it is feasible to do further testing. The following is a summary of the final data instrument test results.

Table 2. Output Outer test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Employee Management	0.959	0.966	0.781
Employee Performance	0.983	0.985	0.781
Knowledge Management	0.951	0.959	0.747
Talent Management	0.955	0.960	0.689

Source: Data Processed, 2023

Reliability Test

On each statement, the reliability test was run simultaneously. The instrument is deemed credible if the correlation coefficient is positive and significant. The SmartPLS 4.0 application helped with reliability testing in this investigation. Cronbach Alpha results can be shown. The statement items or questions in the questionnaire are considered to be credible if valueCronbach Alpha > 0.7 (Ghozali, 2021). Additionally, if the value composite reliability > 0.70, the value of the study's questionnaire is

considered reliable (Ghozali, 2021). Based on the test results of Table 2 it can be seen that the results' composite reliability nor Cronbach's alpha showed a satisfactory value, namely the value of each variable above the minimum value of 0.70 so this study was declared reliable.

Hypothesis test

The hypothesis test in this study uses path analysis which is tested through Smart PLS with the four hypotheses proposed. The evaluation criterion is the P-Value ≤ 0.05 , so the hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3. Output Outer test

Variable	Original Sample (O)	Sample Average (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
<i>Talent Management -> Employee Performance</i>	0.329	0.347	0.141	2,493	0.020
<i>Knowledge Management -> Employee Performance</i>	0.215	0.218	0.102	2.134	0.035
<i>Talent Management -> Employee Engagement -> Employee Performance</i>	0.278	0.261	0.102	2,729	0.007
<i>Knowledge Management -> Employee Engagement -> Employee Performance</i>	0.154	0.145	0.075	2062	0.040

Source: Data Processed, 2023

1. The direct influence of Talent Management on Employee Performance.

The results of the study show the first hypothesis, namely that talent management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta, which is a strong factor in determining employee performance. Through tests that have been carried out with a coefficient of 0.329 with a significance level of p-values of 0.020 less than 0.05.

2. Direct influence of Knowledge Management on Employee Performance..

The results of this study indicate that knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta. Through tests that have been carried out with a coefficient of 0.215 with a significance level of p-values of 0.035 less than 0.05.

3. Indirect Influence of Talent Management on Employee Performance Through Employee Engagement

The results of this study indicate that talent management through employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta. Through tests that have been carried out with a coefficient of 0.278 with a significance level of p-values of 0.007 less than 0.05.

4. Indirect Influence of Knowledge Management on Employee Performance Through Employee Engagement

The results of this study indicate that talent management through employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta. Through tests that have been carried out with a coefficient of 0.278 with a significance level of p-values of 0.007 less than 0.05.

DISCUSSION

1. There are three indicators of talent management, namely recruitment, retain and development. The indicator with the highest score is the development indicator. For this reason, the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS must continue to encourage employees to attend training and development according to the type of work. In addition, the lowest indicator is on the retain indicator, it is hoped that BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta Leaders can assist in achieving the career targets of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta employees. The results of this study indicate that talent management is very important in improving employee performance so that the higher the talent management, the employee performance at the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS will increase. Therefore, it is important for BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB

Yogyakarta to pay attention to what factors cause high and low talent management. *Talent management* is an important matter related to the management of human resources as an asset of a company or organization. Improving employee performance cannot be separated from talent management. If talent management can be carried out in an integrated and appropriate manner, it can improve employee performance. Vice versa if talent management is not implemented optimally, employee performance will decrease (Harmen, 2018).

2. There are three indicators of knowledge management, namely personal knowledge, work procedures and technology. The indicator with the highest score on the work procedure indicator, BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta employees have completed the work according to the specified minimum standard of work. In addition, the lowest indicator on the technology indicator shows that the use of information technology to access additional work-related knowledge is still often misused by employees for non-work interests. The results of this study indicate that knowledge management is very important in improving employee performance so that the higher the knowledge management, the employee performance at the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS will increase. Therefore, The role of knowledge management is very important in organizational life as a form of strategy in improving employee performance. "Knowledge management can improve skills and work motivation so as to encourage increased individual and organizational performance. Employee performance will achieve maximum results if it is supported by the knowledge it has, but vice versa if knowledge management is not good, it will have an impact on decreasing performance (Falah, 2017).
3. There are three indicators of talent management, namely recruitment, retain and development and indicators of employee engagement, there are three indicators, namely vigor, dedication and absorption. The employee engagement indicator with the highest score is on the absorption indicator, because the working relationship between the Yogyakarta KACAB BPJS Ketenagakerjaan employees and their superiors is very pleasant. In addition, the lowest indicator on the absorption indicator is the employment relationship between the Yogyakarta KACAB BPJS employees and employees who are still unpleasant. The results of this study indicate that talent management through employee engagement is very important in improving employee performance so that the higher the talent management through employee engagement, the employee performance at the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS will increase. Therefore, it is important for BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta to pay attention to the factors that cause high and low talent management through employee engagement.
4. The results of this study indicate that knowledge management through employee engagement is very important in improving employee performance so that the higher the knowledge management through employee engagement, the employee performance at the Yogyakarta KACAB Employment BPJS will increase. Therefore, it is important for BPJS Ketenagakerjaan KACAB Yogyakarta to pay attention to what factors cause high and low knowledge management.

Supporting the results of this research, there is research conducted by Sumarto & Rumaningsih, (2021) found that there are direct and indirect impacts on the talent management and knowledge management variables indicating that the two pathways are effective, so that the talent management and knowledge management variables need to be maintained. This research also shows that there is a direct and indirect positive and significant influence between talent management and knowledge management on employee performance, so that employee engagement as a mediating variable is a partial mediation. The results of this study are supported by research by Choirun et al., (2016) which shows knowledge management also has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. So that, Abdullahi et al., (2022) which shows talent management positive but not significant effect on employee performance through employee engagement as a mediating variable

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